

IKKI O'ZGARUVCHILI TENGSIZLIKLAR SISTEMASINI TAQQOSLAMALAR USULI BILAN YECHISH.

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ANNOTATSIYA.

Maqolada tengsizliklar sistemasini yechish, bu o'zgaruvchining-sistemaning har bir tengsizligini qanoatlantiradigan barcha qiymatlari to'plamini topish o'rganilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Tekislik nuqtalari, chiziqli tengsizliklar, to'plam, doira

ANNOTATION.

Plane points, linear inequalities, set, circle.

Ikki o'zgaruvchili tengsizliklar sistemasini taqqoslash, matematikada juda muhim o'rin tutadi. Bu usul, o'zgaruvchilar funksiyalari, limitlar, integrallar va koordinatalar orqali tengsizliklarini taqqoslashga asoslangan.

Bir o'zgaruvchili ikki yoki undan ortiq chiziqli tengsizliklar to'plamiga bir o'zgaruvchili *chiziqli tengsizliklar sistemasi* deyiladi.

Tengsizliklar sistemasini yechish, bu o'zgaruvchining-sistemaning har bir tengsizligini qanoatlantiradigan barcha qiymatlari to'plamini topish demakdir.

Bir o'zgaruvchili (noma'lumli) ikkita chiziqli tengsizliklar sistemasini

$$\begin{cases} a_1x + b_1 > 0 \\ a_2x + b_2 > 0 \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

qaraymiz. Bu sistemaning har bir tengsizligini alohida-alohida yechganda, quyidagi hollar bo'lishi mumkin.

1. Har bir tengsizlikning yechimida bir xil ma'noli tengsizlik bo'ladi, ya'ni

$$a) \begin{cases} x > m \\ x > n \end{cases}$$

Bunda $m > n$ bo'lsa, sistemaning yechimlarini topish uchun sonlar o'qini olib, unda birinchi (yuqorida) va ikkinchi (pastda) tengsizliklarning yechimlarini belgilaymiz. Bu tengsizliklar yechimlarining umumiy qismiga mos $x > m$ qiymatlar sistemaning yechimi bo'ladi. Uni $(m, +\infty)$ deb yozamiz.

$$b) \begin{cases} x < m \\ x < n \end{cases}$$

Bunda $m > n$ bo'lsa, sistemaning yechimlari $x < n$, ya'ni $(-\infty, n)$ to'plamdan iborat.

2. Har bir tengsizlikning yechimida qarama-qarshi ma'noli tengsizliklar bo'ladi, ya'ni

$$a) \begin{cases} x > m \\ x < n \end{cases}$$

Bunda $m < n$ bo'lsa, sistemaning yechimlari $m < x < n$, ya'ni (m, n) to'plamdan iborat bo'ladi.

$$b) \begin{cases} x < m \\ x > n \end{cases}$$

Bunda $m < n$ bo'lsa, sistemaning tengsizliklari bir-biriga zid yechimlarga ega bo'lib, sistema yechimga ega bo'lmaydi, ya'ni yechimlar to'plami bo'sh to'plam bo'ladi.

(2) sistemada tengsizlik belgilari har xil bo'lishi ham mumkin, masalan, birinchisida ">" ikkinchisida "<", yoki " \geq " va " \leq ", ">" va " \leq " va hokozo. Bunday hollarda ham sistema yuqoridagiga o'xshash yechiladi.

Endi ikki noma'lumli tengsizliklar sistemasini qaraymiz. Bunday sistemalarning umumiy ko'rinishi

$$\begin{cases} f(x, y) > 0 \\ \varphi(x, y) > 0 \end{cases}$$

dan iborat (tengsizlik belgilari har xil bo'lishi mumkin). Bu yerdagi har bir tengsizlik tekislikda qandaydir sohani tasvirlaydi. Berilgan sistemaning yechimlar to'plami shu sohalarning umumiy qismidan iborat bo'ladi (bo'sh to'plam bo'lishi ham mumkin). Masalan, ushbu

$$\begin{cases} y \geq 2 \\ x^2 + y^2 \leq 36 \end{cases}$$

sistemani qaraymiz. U berilgan tengsizliklar kon'yunksiyasidan iborat: $(y \geq 2) \wedge (x^2 + y^2 \leq 36)$. Osongina ko'rish mumkinki, bu sistemaning grafigi markazi koordinata boshida va radiusi 6 ga teng bo'lgan doira bilan $y=2$ to'g'ri chiziqdan yuqorida joylashgan tekislikning umumiy qismidan iborat. Yuqoridagi (3) sistemaning xususiy holi bo'lgan *ikki o'zgaruvchili chiziqli tengsizliklar sistemasini* qaraymiz.

$$\begin{cases} a_1x + b_1y + c_1 < 0 \\ a_2x + b_2y + c_2 > 0 \end{cases}$$

Bu sistemada $a_1x + b_1y + c_1 = 0$ va $a_2x + b_2y + c_2 = 0$ to'g'ri chiziqlar o'zaro parallel emas deb olamiz. Faraz qilaylik, bu sistemaning har bir tengsizligini y ka nisbatan yechib,

$$\begin{cases} y < kx + b \\ y > px + q \end{cases}$$

sistemani hosil qilgan bo'laylik. x o'zgaruvchining biror qiymatida bu sistema tengsizliklari o'rinli bo'lishi uchun

$px+q < kx+b$ yoki $(p-k)x < b-q$ bajarilishi zarur va yetarli (tranzitivlik qonuniga binoan).

Demak, $p > k$ bo'lganda, $x < \frac{b-q}{p-k}$ va $p < k$ bo'lganda, $x > \frac{b-q}{p-k}$ bo'lib

sistemaning umumiy yechimi esa quyidagidan iborat.

$-\infty < x < \frac{b-q}{p-k}$, $px+q < y < kx+b$ agar $p > k$ bo'lsa va

$\frac{b-q}{p-k} < x < +\infty$, $px+q < y < kx+b$ agar $p < k$ bo'lsa.

Ravshanki, berilgan sistemaning grafigi tekislikda $y=px+q$ to'g'ri chiziqdan yuqoridagi va $y=kx+b$ to'g'ri chiziqdan pastdagi tekislik nuqtalari to'plamidan iborat.

(4) tengsizlikda tengsizlik belgilari turlicha yoki bir xil bo'lishi mumkin. Bundan tashqari, undagi va to'g'ri chiziqlar parallel ham bo'lishi mumkin.

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